

ON e^* -REGULARITY AND e^* -NORMALITY IN INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

S. SIVASANGARI AND G. SARAVANAKUMAR*

ABSTRACT. In this paper, the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open and e^* -closed sets to introduce some new types of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -separation axioms, intuitionistic fuzzy e^*-T_i space (for $i = 3, 4$) and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular and e^* -normal spaces are introduced, some theorems about them are investigated. Stronger forms of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -normal spaces are introduced. Moreover, the relationships between these separation axioms and others are investigated.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ever since the introduction of fuzzy sets by Zadeh [32], the fuzzy concept has invaded almost all branches of mathematics. The concept of fuzzy topological spaces was introduced and developed by Chang [6]. Atanassov [1] introduced the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy sets, Coker [7] introduced the intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces. Several authors [2, 15, 20, 26] introduced the concepts of fuzzy separation axioms using the notion of fuzzy open set and Othman and Latha [20] by using the notions of fuzzy regular open sets, fuzzy β -open sets, fuzzy α -open sets and fuzzy semi α -open sets respectively. Singal and Prakash [25] have introduced the concept of fuzzy pre-separation axioms. Qahtani and Al-Qubati [21] have introduced and studied new kinds of fuzzy pre-separation axioms. Several notions based on fuzzy pre-separation axioms have been studied. Some authors studied the concept of separation axioms in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces. In 2001, Bayhan and Coker [3] gave some characterizations of T_1 and T_2 separation axioms in intuitionistic topological spaces, they gave interrelations between several types of separation axioms and some counter examples. In 2003, Lupianez [17] defined new notions of Hausdorffness in the intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces. In 2005, Bayhan and Coker [5] studied pairwise separation axioms in double intuitionistic topological spaces. For more studies, we can find them in [4, 9, 18, 24]. The initiations of e^* -open sets, e^* -continuity and e^* -compactness in topological spaces are due to Ekici [10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. Sobana et.al

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*Corresponding author.

[29] were introduced the concept of fuzzy e^* -open sets, fuzzy e^* -continuity and fuzzy e^* -compactness in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces (briefly., IFTS's). The main purpose of this paper is to introduce and study some new types of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -separation axioms, which is intuitionistic fuzzy e^* - T_i space (for, $i = 3, 4$) and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -normal spaces by using the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open (resp. closed) sets. Also, we will introduce stronger forms of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -normal spaces with relationships between these separation axioms and others

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. [1] Let X be a nonempty fixed set and I be the closed interval in $[0, 1]$. An intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) A is an object of the following form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$ where the mappings $\mu_A(x) : X \rightarrow I$ and $\nu_A(x) : X \rightarrow I$ denote the degree of membership (namely) $\mu_A(x)$ and the degree of non membership (namely) $\nu_A(x)$ for each element $x \in X$ to the set A respectively, and $0 \leq \mu_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1$ for each $x \in X$.

Definition 2.2. [1] Let A and B are intuitionistic fuzzy sets of the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$ and $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \nu_B(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$. Then

- (i) $A \subseteq B$ if and only if $\mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \nu_B(x)$;
- (ii) \bar{A} (or A^c) = $\{ \langle x, \nu_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$;
- (iii) $A \cap B = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \nu_A(x) \vee \nu_B(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$;
- (iv) $A \cup B = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \nu_A(x) \wedge \nu_B(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$;
- (v) $[]A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), 1 - \mu_A(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$;
- (vi) $\langle \rangle A = \{ \langle x, 1 - \nu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$;

We will use the notation $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A, \nu_A \rangle; x \in X \}$ instead of $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$.

Definition 2.3. [7] $\mathbb{0} = \{ \langle x, 0, 1 \rangle; x \in X \}$ and $\mathbb{1} = \{ \langle x, 1, 0 \rangle; x \in X \}$. Let $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ such that $\alpha + \beta \leq 1$. An intuitionistic fuzzy point $(IFP)_{p(\alpha, \beta)}$ is

intuitionistic fuzzy set defined by $p_{(\alpha, \beta)}(x) = \begin{cases} (\alpha, \beta) & \text{if } x=p \\ (0, 1) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Definition 2.4. [7] An intuitionistic fuzzy topology (IFT) in Coker's sense on a nonempty set X is a family T of intuitionistic fuzzy sets in X satisfying the following axioms:

- (i) $\mathbb{0}, \mathbb{1} \in T$;
- (ii) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in T$, for any $G_1, G_2 \in T$;
- (iii) $\cup G_i \in T$ for any arbitrary family $\{G_i; i \in J\} \subseteq T$.

In this paper by (X, T) or simply by X we will denote the intuitionistic fuzzy topological space (IFTS). Each IFS which belongs to T is called an intuitionistic fuzzy open set (IFOS) in X . The complement \bar{A} of an IFOS A in X is called an intuitionistic fuzzy closed set (IFCS) in X .

Definition 2.5. [16] Let $p_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ be an IFP in IFTS X . An IFS A in X is called an intuitionistic fuzzy neighborhood (IFN) of $p_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ if there exists an IFOS B in X such that $p_{(\alpha, \beta)} \in B \subseteq A$.

Let X and Y are two non-empty sets and $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a function [7]. If $B = \{ \langle y, \mu_B(y), \nu_B(y) \rangle; y \in Y \}$ is an IFS in Y , then the pre-image of B under f is denoted and defined by $f^{-1}(B) = \{ \langle x, f^{-1}(\mu_B(x)), f^{-1}(\nu_B(x)) \rangle; x \in X \}$. Since

$\mu_B(x)$, $\nu_B(x)$ are fuzzy sets, we explain that $f^{-1}(\mu_B(x)) = \mu_B(x)(f(x))$, $f^{-1}(\nu_B(x)) = \nu_B(x)(f(x))$.

Definition 2.6. [7] Let (X, T) be an IFTS and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A, \nu_A \rangle; x \in X \}$ be an IFS in X . Then the intuitionistic fuzzy closure and intuitionistic fuzzy interior of A are defined by

- (i) $cl(A) = \bigcap \{ C : C \text{ is an IFCS in } X \text{ and } C \supseteq A \}$;
- (ii) $int(A) = \bigcup \{ D : D \text{ is an IFOS in } X \text{ and } D \subseteq A \}$;

It can be also shown that $cl(A)$ is an IFCS, $int(A)$ is an IFOS in X and A is an IFCS in X if and only if $cl(A) = A$; A is an IFOS in X if and only if $int(A) = A$

Proposition 2.1. [7] Let (X, T) be an IFTS and A, B be intuitionistic fuzzy sets in X . Then the following properties hold:

- (i) $cl(\overline{A}) = \overline{(int(A))}$, $int(\overline{A}) = \overline{(cl(A))}$;
- (ii) $int(A) \subseteq A \subseteq cl(A)$.

Definition 2.7. Let A be IFS in an IFTS (X, T) . A is called an intuitionistic fuzzy regular open set [30] (briefly *IFROS*) if $A = intcl(A)$ and intuitionistic fuzzy regular closed set (briefly *IFRCS*) if $A = clint(A)$

Definition 2.8. [30] Let (X, T) be an IFTS and $A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle$ be a IFS in X . Then the fuzzy δ closure of A are denoted and defined by $cl_\delta(A) = \bigcap \{ K : K \text{ is an IFRCS in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K \}$ and $int_\delta(A) = \bigcup \{ G : G \text{ is an IFROS in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}$.

Definition 2.9. [29] Let A be an IFS in an IFTS (X, T) . A is called an intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open set (*IFe*OS*, for short) in X if $A \subseteq clintcl_\delta(A)$

Definition 2.10. [27] Let (X, T) be an IFTS and $A = \langle x, \mu_A, \nu_A \rangle$ be an IFS in X . Then the intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -interior and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -closure are defined and denoted by:

$$cl_{e^*}(A) = \bigcap \{ K : K \text{ is an IFe*CS in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K \}$$

and

$$int_{e^*}(A) = \bigcup \{ G : G \text{ is an IFe*OS in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}.$$

It is clear that A is an IFe*CS (*IFe*OS*) in X iff $A = cl_{e^*}(A)$ ($A = int_{e^*}(A)$).

Definition 2.11. [7] Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be IFTS's. A function $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is called intuitionistic fuzzy continuous (resp., e^* -continuous [29]) if $f^{-1}(B)$ is an IFOS (resp., *IFe*OS*) in X for every $B \in S$.

Definition 2.12. [28] A IFTS (X, T) is said to be a intuitionistic fuzzy stronger- e^* - T_1 (briefly, *IFe*-T₁s*) if every IFP is an IFe*CS.

3. e^* -REGULARITY IN INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Definition 3.1. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -Uryshon (briefly, *IFe*-T₂^{1/2}*) if for every pair of IFP's $p = x_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, $q = y_{(\gamma, \eta)}$ with different supports, there exists an *IFe*OS*'s M and N such that $(p \subseteq M, q \not\subseteq M)$ and $(q \subseteq N, p \not\subseteq N)$ and $IFe*cl(M) \not\subseteq IFe*cl(N)$.

Definition 3.2. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular space (briefly, *IFe*Rs*) if for every pair of IFP p and *IFe*CS* N such that $p \not\subseteq N$ there exists an *IFe*OS*'s M_1 and M_2 such that $(p \subseteq M_1, N \subseteq M_2 \text{ and } M_1 \not\subseteq M_2)$.

Theorem 3.1. *If (X, T) be an IFe^*Rs , then for any IFP $p = x_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ and an IFOS N such that $p \subseteq N$, there exists an IFe^*OS M_1 such that $p \subseteq M_1 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_1) \subseteq N$.*

Proof. Suppose that X be an IFe^*Rs . Let $N = \langle x, \mu_N(x), \gamma_N(x) \rangle$ be an IFOS of X and p be an IFP in X such that $p \subseteq N$. Then $N^c = \langle x, \gamma_N(x), \mu_N(x) \rangle$ is an IFe^*CS in X . Since X is an IFe^*Rs , therefore there exist two IFe^*OS 's M_1 and M_2 such that $p \in M_1, N^c \subseteq M_2$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$. Now M_2^c is an IFe^*CS such that $M_1 \subseteq M_2^c \subseteq N$, thus, $p \in M_1 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_1)$ and $IFe^*cl(M_1) \subseteq M_2^c \subseteq N$, so $IFe^*cl(M_1) \subseteq N$. Hence $p \subseteq M_1 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_1) \subseteq N$. \square

Definition 3.3. A IFTS (X, T) is said to be an intuitionistic fuzzy e^*T_3 space (briefly, IFe^*T_3) if it is an IFe^*Rs as well as $IFe^* - T_1$ s space.

Proposition 3.2. *Every subspace of IFe^*Rs is IFe^*Rs .*

Proof. Let (X, T) be a IFe^*Rs and Y be subspace of X . To prove that Y is an IFe^* -regular, where $T_Y = \{G_Y = \langle x, \mu_{G|Y}(x), \nu_{G|Y}(x) \rangle, x \in Y, G \in T\}$ and $G = \langle x, \mu_G(x), \nu_G(x) \rangle$. Let $p = x_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ be an IFP in Y , and N_Y be an IFe^*CS in Y such that $p \not\subseteq N_Y$. Since Y is a subspace of X , so $p \in X$ and there exist an IFe^*CS F in X such that the closed set generated by it for Y is F_Y . Since X is IFe^*Rs such that $p \not\subseteq F$, there exist two IFe^*OS 's M_1, M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_1 = \langle x, \mu_{M_1}(x), \nu_{M_1}(x) \rangle$ and $N \subseteq M_1 = \langle x, \mu_{M_2}(x), \nu_{M_2}(x) \rangle$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2, M_{1Y} = \langle x, \mu_{M_1|Y}(x), \nu_{M_1|Y}(x) \rangle$ and $M_{2Y} = \langle x, \mu_{M_2|Y}(x), \nu_{M_2|Y}(x) \rangle$ are IFe^*OS in Y such that that $p \subseteq M_{1Y}, N \subseteq M_{2Y}$ and $M_{1Y} \not\subseteq M_{2Y}$. Hence Y is an IFe^*Rs . \square

Theorem 3.3. *An IFTS (X, T) is said to be an IFe^*Rs if and only if for an IFP $p = x_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ and an IFCS N such that $p \not\subseteq N$, there exist two IFe^*OS 's M_1, M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_1, N \subseteq M_2$, and $IFe^*cl(M_1) \not\subseteq (IFe^*cl(M_2))$.*

Proof. Since $p \not\subseteq N$ and (X, T) is IFe^*Rs , there exist two IFe^*OS 's M_1, M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_1, N \subseteq M_2$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$ and by Theorem 3.1 $p \subseteq M_2 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2) \subseteq M_1$. Hence $IFe^*cl(M_2) \subseteq M_1$. Also, $N \subseteq M_2 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2)$. But since $IFe^*cl(M_1) \not\subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2)$, then $N \subseteq M_2 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2) \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_1) \subseteq M_1^c$ and hence $p \subseteq M_1, N \subseteq M_2$ and $IFe^*cl(M_1) \not\subseteq (IFe^*cl(M_2))$. \square

The converse is clear. \square

Theorem 3.4. *Let (X, T) be an IFe^*Rs which is also IFT_0 . Then (X, T) is $IFe^*-T_{2\frac{1}{2}}$.*

Proof. Let $p = x_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ and $q = x_{(\gamma, \eta)}$ are IFP's with different supports. Since (X, T) is an IFT_0 space, then there exists an IFOS N such that $p \subseteq N, q \not\subseteq N$ or $q \subseteq N, p \not\subseteq N$. Consider the part $p \subseteq N, q \not\subseteq N$. This implies that $p \not\subseteq N^c$ where N^c is an IFCS. Since (X, T) is an IFe^*Rs , so by Theorem 3.3, there exist an IFe^*OS 's M_1 and M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_1$ and $N^c \subseteq M_2$ and $IFe^*cl(M_1) \not\subseteq (IFe^*cl(M_2))$ or $p \subseteq M_1, q \subseteq M_2$ and $IFe^*cl(M_1) \not\subseteq (IFe^*cl(M_2))$. Hence (X, T) is $IFe^*T_{2\frac{1}{2}}$. \square

Theorem 3.5. *If $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is a closed injective intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -continuous mapping and (Y, S) is an IFRS, then (X, T) is an IFe^*Rs .*

Proof. Let p be an IFP and N be an IFCS in X . Then $f(p)$ is an IFP and $f(N)$ is an IFCS in Y . Since (Y, S) is an intuitionistic fuzzy regular space then there exist two IFOS's M_1 and M_2 such that $f(N) \subseteq M_2, f(p) \subseteq M_1$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$. It follows that $N \subseteq f^{-1}(M_2), p \subseteq f^{-1}(M_1)$ and $f^{-1}(M_1) \subseteq f^{-1}(M_2)$ where $f^{-1}(M_1)$ and $f^{-1}(M_2)$ are IFe^*OS 's in X . Hence (X, T) is an IFe^*Rs . \square

Theorem 3.6. Let $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open mapping. If X is an intuitionistic fuzzy regular space then Y is IFe^*Rs .

Theorem 3.7. Every IFe^*Rs and IFT_2 space is an $IFe^*T_{2\frac{1}{2}}$ space.

Proof. Let (X, T) be an IFTS which is IFe^*Rs and IFT_2 . Let p and q be two IFP's with different supports in X . Since X is an IFT_2 , there exist two IFOS's M and N such that $p \subseteq M, q \not\subseteq M, q \subseteq N, p \not\subseteq N$ and $M \not\subseteq N$ or $IFe^*cl(M) \not\subseteq N$. So that $q \not\subseteq M$. Since $IFe^*cl(M)$ is an IFCS and (X, T) is an IFe^*Rs . So by Proposition 3.2, there exist an IFe^*OS 's M_1 and M_2 such that $IFe^*cl(M) \subseteq M_2, q \subseteq M_1$ and $IFe^*cl(M_1) \not\subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2)$. Since $p \subseteq IFe^*cl(M)$, we have $p \subseteq M_2, q \subseteq M_1$, and $IFe^*cl(M_1) \not\subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2)$. Hence the space (X, T) is $IFe^*T_{2\frac{1}{2}}$ space. \square

Definition 3.4. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be

- (i) intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular space (i) (briefly, $IFe^*Rs(i)$) if for an IFP p and an IFe^*CS N such that $p \not\subseteq N$, there exist two IFe^*OS 's M_1 and M_2 such that $N \subseteq M_2, p \subseteq M_1$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$.
- (ii) intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular space (ii) (briefly, $IFe^*Rs(ii)$) if for an IFP p and an IFe^*CS N such that $p \not\subseteq N$, there exist two IFOS's M_1 and M_2 such that $N \subseteq M_2, p \subseteq M_1$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$.

Theorem 3.8. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be

- (i) $IFe^*Rs(i)$ if for an IFP p and an IFe^*OS M_1 such that $p \subseteq M_1$, there exist an IFe^*OS M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_2 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2) \subseteq M_1$.
- (ii) $IFe^*Rs(ii)$ if for an IFP p and an IFe^*OS M_1 such that $p \subseteq M_1$, there exist an IFOS M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_2 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2) \subseteq M_1$.

Proof. (i) Let M_1 be an IFe^*OS such that $p \subseteq M_1$, then $p \not\subseteq M_1^c$ and M_1^c is an IFe^*CS . Therefore, there exist two IFOS's N and K such that $p \subseteq N, M_1^c \subseteq K$ and $N \not\subseteq K$. Now, we can get $IFe^*cl(N)^c \subseteq (M_1^c)^c = M_1$ and $P \subseteq N \subseteq IFe^*cl(N) \subseteq M_1$. It is clear that $p \subseteq N \subseteq IFe^*int(IFe^*cl(N) \subseteq IFe^*cl(N) \subseteq M_1)$. Therefore, if we put $IFe^*int(IFe^*cl(N) = M_2$, then $p \subseteq N \subseteq M_2 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2) \subseteq M_1$, where M_2 is an IFOS. The converse is clear.

(ii) The proof is similar to (i). \square

Theorem 3.9. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be

- (i) $IFe^*Rs(i)$ if for an IFP p and an IFe^*CS N such that $p \not\subseteq N^c$, there exist two IFe^*OS 's M_1 and M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_1, N \subseteq M_2$, and $IFe^*cl(M_1) \not\subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2)$.
- (ii) $IFe^*Rs(ii)$ if for an IFP p and an IFe^*CS N such that $p \not\subseteq N$, there exist two IFOS's M_1 and M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_1, N \subseteq M_2$, and $IFe^*cl(M_1) \not\subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2)$.

Proof. Similar to that of Theorem 3.8. \square

Theorem 3.10. Let f be an injective, intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -irresolute mapping from an IFTS (X, T) into an IFTS (Y, S) . Then X is e^*Rs if Y is e^*Rs .

Theorem 3.11. Let (X, T) be an $IFe^*Rs(i)$ which is also IFe^*T_0 . Then (X, T) is $IFe^*T_{2\frac{1}{2}}$.

Proof. Let p and q are IFP's with different supports. Since (X, T) is a IFe^*T_0 space, then there exists an IFe^*OS M such that $p \not\subseteq M, q \not\subseteq M$ or $q \subseteq M, p \not\subseteq M$. Consider the part $p \not\subseteq M, q \not\subseteq M$. This implies that $p \subseteq (M^c)^c$, where M^c is an IFe^*CS . Since (X, T) is

$IFe^*Rs(i)$, so by Theorem 3.9, there exist $IFe^*OS's$ N and K such that $p \subseteq N, M^c \subseteq K$ and $IFe^*cl(N) \not\subseteq IFe^*cl(K)$, or $p \subseteq N, q \subseteq K$ and $IFe^*cl(N) \not\subseteq IFe^*cl(K)$. Hence (X, T) is an $IFe^*T_{2\frac{1}{2}}$. \square

Theorem 3.12. *Let (X, T) be an $IFe^*Rs(ii)$ which is also IFe^*T_0 . Then (X, T) is $IFe^*T_{2\frac{1}{2}}$.*

Theorem 3.13. *Let (X, T) be an $IFe^*Rs(ii)$ which is also IFe^*T_2 . Then (X, T) is $IFe^*T_{2\frac{1}{2}}$.*

Definition 3.5. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be

- (i) intuitionistic Fuzzy e^*T_3 space (i) (briefly, $IFe^*T_3s(i)$) if it is $IFe^*Rs(i)$ as well as IFe^*-T_1s space.
- (ii) intuitionistic Fuzzy e^*T_3 space (ii) (briefly, $IFe^*T_3s(ii)$) if it is $IFe^*Rs(ii)$ as well as IFe^*-T_1s space.

4. e^* -NORMALITY IN INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Definition 4.1. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be

- (i) intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -normal space (briefly, IFe^*Ns) if for every pair of IFCS's N_1 and N_2 such that $N_1 \not\subseteq N_2$, there exist two $IFe^*OS's$ M_1 and M_2 such that $N_1 \subseteq M_1, N_2 \subseteq M_2$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$.
- (ii) intuitionistic fuzzy e^*T_4 spac (briefly, IFe^*T_4s)e if it is an IFe^*Ns as well as IFe^*-T_1s space.

Theorem 4.1. *An IFTS (X, T) is an IFe^*Ns if and only if for every IFCS N_1 and every IFOS N_2 such that $N_1 \subseteq N_2$ there exists an IFe^*OS M such that $N_1 \subseteq M \subseteq IFe^*cl(M) \subseteq N_2$.*

Proof. Let (X, T) be an IFe^*Ns and let $N_1 \subseteq N_2$, where N_1 is a IFCS and N_2 is an IFOS, then $(N_2)^c$ is an IFCS but (X, T) be an IFe^*Ns hence there exist two $IFe^*OS's$ M_1 and M_2 such that $N_1 \subseteq M_1, (N_2)^c \subseteq M_2$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$, therefore $N_1 \subseteq M \subseteq (M_2)^c \subseteq N_2$ that implies $IFe^*cl(N_1) \subseteq IFe^*cl(M) \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_2)^c \subseteq IFe^*cl(N_2)$, then $N_1 \subseteq IFe^*cl(N_1) \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_1) \subseteq (M_2)^c \subseteq N_2$. Hence $N_1 \subseteq M_1 \subseteq IFe^*cl(M_1) \subseteq N_2$. The converse is clear. \square

Theorem 4.2. *If $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is closed injective, intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -continuous mapping and (Y, S) is a intuitionistic fuzzy normal space, then (X, T) is an IFe^*Ns .*

Theorem 4.3. *If $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open mapping. Then (X, T) is a intuitionistic fuzzy normal space, if (Y, S) is an IFe^*Ns .*

Theorem 4.4. *Every IFe^*Ns and IFTs space is IFe^*Rs .*

Proof. Let (X, T) be an IFe^*Ns and IFTs space. Let p and N be respectively, an IFP and IFe^*CS in X and $p \not\subseteq N$. Since (X, T) is IFTS, then p is an IFe^*CS and since (X, T) is an IFe^*Ns , there exist $IFe^*OS's$ M_1 and M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_1, N \subseteq M_2$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$. Hence (X, T) is an IFe^*Rs . \square

Definition 4.2. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be

- (i) intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -normal space (i) (briefly, $IFe^*Ns(i)$) if for every pair of $IFe^*CS's$ N_1 and N_2 such that $N_1 \not\subseteq N_2$, there exist two $IFe^*OS's$ M_1 and M_2 such that $N_1 \subseteq M_1, N_2 \subseteq M_2$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$.

- (ii) intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -normal space (ii) (briefly, $IFe^*Ns(ii)$) if for every pair of $IFe^*CS's$ N_1 and N_2 such that $N_1 \not\subseteq N_2$, there exist two IFOS's M_1 and M_2 such that $N_1 \subseteq M_1, N_2 \subseteq M_2$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$.

Theorem 4.5. (1) Every $IFe^*Ns(i)$ and IFe^*Ts space is $IFe^*Rs(i)$.

(2) Every $IFe^*Ns(ii)$ and IFe^*Ts space is $IFe^*Rs(ii)$.

Proof. (1) Let (X, T) be an $IFe^*Ns(i)$ and IFe^*Ts space. Let p and N be respectively, an IFP and an IFe^*CS in X and $p \not\subseteq N$. Since (X, T) is IFe^*Ts , then p is an IFe^*CS and since (X, T) is $IFe^*Ns(i)$, there exist an $IFe^*OS's$ M_1 and M_2 such that $p \subseteq M_1, N \subseteq M_2$ and $M_1 \not\subseteq M_2$. Hence (X, T) is an $IFe^*Rs(i)$.

Proof for case (2) is similarly follow. □

Definition 4.3. An IFTS (X, T) is said to be

- (i) intuitionistic fuzzy e^*T_4 space (i) (briefly, $IFe_4^T s(i)$) if it is $IFe^*Ns(i)$ as well as IFe^*-T_1s space.
(ii) intuitionistic fuzzy e^*T_4 space (ii) (briefly, $IFe_4^T s(ii)$) if it is $IFe^*Ns(ii)$ as well as IFe^*-T_1s space.

Theorem 4.6. (1) Every $IFe^*T_4s(i)$ is $IFe^*T_3s(i)$

(2) Every $IFe^*T_4s(ii)$ is $IFe^*T_3s(ii)$

Proof. Strictly follow from Theorem 4.5 □

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced and studied the concepts of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -open and e^* -closed sets to some new types of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -separation axioms, intuitionistic fuzzy e^*-T_i space (for $i = 3, 4$) and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular and e^* -normal spaces are introduced, some theorems about them are investigated. Stronger forms of intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -regular and intuitionistic fuzzy e^* -normal spaces are introduced. Moreover, the relationships between these separation axioms and others are investigated.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. T. Atanassov, Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 20, (1986), 87-96.
- [2] G. Balasubramanian, Fuzzy β open sets and fuzzy β separation axioms, Kybernetika, 32(2) (1999), 215-223.
- [3] S Bayhan and D. Coker, On fuzzy separation axioms in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Busefal, 67 (1996), 77-87.
- [4] S. Bayhan and D. Coker, On separation axioms in intuitionistic topological spaces, Intern. Jour. Math. Sci. 27(10) (2001), 621-630.
- [5] S. Bayhan and D. Coker, Pairwise separation axioms in intuitionistic topological spaces, Hacettepe Journal of Mathematics and Statistics, 34 (2005), 101-114.
- [6] C. L. Chang, Fuzzy topological spaces, J. Math. Anal. Appl., 24, (1968), 182-190.
- [7] D. Coker, An introduction to intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 88, (1997), 81-89.
- [8] D. Coker and M. Demirci, On intuitionistic fuzzy points, NIFS, 1 (2), (1995), 79-84.
- [9] D. Coker, An introduction to fuzzy subspaces in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Journal of fuzzy mathematics, 4 (1996) 749-764.

- [10] E. Ekici, On e -open sets, DP^* -sets and DPe^* -sets and decompositions of continuity, Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering, 33 (2A)(2008), 269-282.
- [11] E. Ekici, Some generalizations of almost contra-super-continuity, Filomat, 21 (2) (2007), 31-44.
- [12] E. Ekici, New forms of contra-continuity, Carpathian Journal of Mathematics, bf 24 (1) (2008), 37-45.
- [13] E. Ekici, On e^* -open sets and $(D, S)^*$ -sets, Mathematica Moravica, 13 (1) (2009), 29-36.
- [14] E. Ekici, A note on a -open sets and e^* -open sets, Filomat, 22 (1) (2008), 89-96.
- [15] M.H. Ghanim, E.E. Kerre and A.S. Mashhour, Separation axioms, subspace and sums in fuzzy topology, J. Math.Anal.Appl. 102 (1984), 189-202.
- [16] S. J. Lee and E. P. Lee, The category of intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Bull. Korean Math. Soc., 37(1) (2000), 63-76.
- [17] F.G. Lupianez, Hausdorffness in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Mathware soft comp. 10 (2003) 17-22.
- [18] F.G. Lupianez, Separation in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, 17(1) (2004), 29-34.
- [19] F.S. Mahmoud, M.A. Fath Alla and S.M. Abd Ellah, Fuzzy topology on fuzzy sets, fuzzy semicontinuity and fuzzy semiseparation axioms, Appl.Math.Comput. 153 (2004),127-140.
- [20] H.A. Othman and S. Latha, On fuzzy α separation axioms, Bull.Kerala Math Asso. 5(1) (2009), 31-38.
- [21] H.AI. Qahtani and Abdul Gawad Al-Qubati, On fuzzy pre-separation axioms, Journal of Advanced Studies in Topology, 4(4) (2013), 1-6.
- [22] R. Santhi and D. Jayanthi, Generalised semi-pre connectedness in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics, 3(2), (2012), 243-253.
- [23] V. Seenivasan and K. Kamala, Fuzzy e -continuity and fuzzy e -open sets, Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics, 8, (1) (2014), 141-148.
- [24] A.K. Singh and R. Srivastava, Separation axioms in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Advances in fuzzy systems, (2012), 1-7.
- [25] M.K. Singal and N. Prakash, Fuzzy pre-open sets and fuzzy pre-separation axioms, fuzzy sets and systems, 44 (1991), 273-281.
- [26] M.K. Singal and N. Rahvansi, Regular open sets in fuzzy topological spaces, fuzzy sets and systems, 50 (1992), 343-353.
- [27] S. Sivasangari, R. Balakumar and G. Saravanakumar, e^* -connectedness in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Annals of Communications in Mathematics, 4(1) (2021), 26-34.
- [28] S. Sivasangari, R. Balakumar and G. Saravanakumar, On e^* -Separation Axioms in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Applied Science and Computer Mathematics, 2(1) (2021), 9-16.
- [29] D. Sobana, V. Chandrasekar and A. Vadivel, On Fuzzy e -open Sets, Fuzzy e -continuity and Fuzzy e -compactness in Intuitionistic Fuzzy Topological Spaces, Sahand Communications in Mathematical Analysis, 12 (1) 2018, 131-153.
- [30] S. S. Thakur and S. Singh, On fuzzy semi-pre open sets and fuzzy semi-pre continuity, Fuzzy Sets and Systems, (1998), 383-391.
- [31] N. Turnali and D. Coker, Fuzzy connectedness in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces, Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 116,(2000), 369-375.
- [32] L. A. Zadeh, Fuzzy Sets, Information and Control, 8, (1965), 338-353.

S. SIVASANGARI,

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, PONNAIYAH RAMAJAYAM INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY (PRIST)
(INSTITUTION DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY), THANJAVUR-613403, TAMILNADU

Email address: sivasangarimaths2020@gmail.com

G. SARAVANAKUMAR

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, VEL TECH RANGARAJAN DR.SAGUNTHALA R&D INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY), AVADI, CHENNAI-600062, INDIA.

Email address: saravananguru2612@gmail.com